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Proposal title: Unifying and disseminating musculoskeletal imaging software
Submission to the call [Advancing imaging through collaborative projects](#) of the Chan-Zuckerberg Initiative

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Table of content of this document:

[A. PROJECT DETAILS](#)

- [1. Project title](#)
- [2. Project purpose](#)
- [3. Abstract/Project Summary](#)
- [4. Type of Project](#)
- [5. Amount Requested](#)
- [6. Milestones](#)
- [7. Expected Impact](#)

[B. PROJECT PROPOSAL](#)

- [Abstract](#)
- [Background](#)
- [Project Goals](#)
- [Significance](#)
- [Project Plan](#)
- [Project Metrics](#)
- [Figures \(Optional\)](#)
- [References](#)

A. PROJECT DETAILS

1. Project title

Unifying and disseminating musculoskeletal imaging software

2. Project purpose

To advance musculoskeletal imaging research by creating a certification system for open, reproducible, and interoperable software and by disseminating software via educational and training activities

3. Abstract/Project Summary

Find it in the project plan ([here](#))

4. Type of Project

- Building capacity
- Training and education

5. Amount Requested

xxx

6. Milestones

Work package 1: Creating and validating a certification framework for open, reproducible, and interoperable MSK imaging research software

1. Creating guidelines for MSK imaging software certification. In the first two quarters of the project, the RSE (Research Software Engineer) and the TAB (Technical Advisory Board) of the ORMIR community will create certification guidelines
2. Developing a certification framework. From the second to the sixth quarter, the RSE will develop the certification framework, following the guidelines created in milestone 1. The framework will be hosted in GitHub and will expose a GitHub action for the project's use.
3. Validating the certification framework. From the fourth to the seventh quarter, the RSE, TAB, and contributors (PI and Co-PIs of this application) to six existing MSK computational projects will jointly work to test and validate the certification framework. Agile practices will be used to clarify certification guidelines, debug and streamline the certification framework, and ultimately converge to robustness and ease of use.
4. Certifying new MSK computational projects. In the last two quarters, the RSE and TAB will jointly coordinate the certification of new software created by the extended MSK imaging community.

Work Package 2: Accelerating adoption and creation of certified MSK imaging software by recruiting and engaging MSK imaging scientists, creating educational material, and providing in-person training and mentoring.

1. Recruiting and engaging MSK imaging scientists. In the first and second quarters, the CAB (Community Advisory Board) will open a Twitter account and redesign the ORMIR community website, which they will maintain for the duration of the project. In the seventh quarter, the PI and Co-PIs will organize a satellite event at QMSKI 2024 to promote the project and engage new contributors. Finally, in the seventh and eighth quarters, the PI and Co-PIs will write scientific publications about the certification framework and the certified projects.
2. Creating an entry point for MSK imaging scientists who are new to open and reproducible research. In the first two quarters, the CAB will design a specific webpage for new members.
 - a. Workshop 1: “*Creating a Jupyter book on open and reproducible software in MSK imaging*” (*Book sprint*). In the third quarter, PI, Co-PIs, RSE, and 12 participants recruited among members of the ORMIR and of the extended QMSKI communities (24 participants in total) will meet for a three-day in-person workshop organized by Fulvia Taddei and her group in October 2023 in Bologna (Italy). After the workshop, the book will be edited by a subcontracted scientific writer to harmonize style.
3. In-person training and mentoring of new MSK software contributors.
 - a. Workshop 2: “*Making your MSK imaging software open, reproducible, and interoperable*” (*Train-the-end-users event*). In the seventh quarter, the PI, Co-PIs, RSE, and 14 participants recruited among QMSKI attendees will meet for a three-day in-person workshop organized by Kathryn Stok and Serena Bonaretti with their teams in Melbourne (Australia). The three most open, reproducible, and interoperable MSK software packages will receive an award.

7. Expected Impact

Impact of MSK software certification and dissemination. We expect to certify 6 existing Python packages while validating the framework and 10 new packages afterwards. We estimate each of the 6 existing packages to be used by at least 2 laboratories of the ORMIR community (e.g. pyKNEEr will be used in Fulvia Taddei’s and Andy Kin On Wong’s laboratories) and beyond the ORMIR community (e.g. BoneErosion will be used in the 81 worldwide laboratories with High Resolution CT scanners, and modified for the 50 (and rising) Photon Counting CT scanners installed worldwide; Muscle-BIDS will be used in 20 collaborating laboratories; and ALBA will be extended to at least 100 scientists already using Bonemat—one of ALBA’s freeware tools). We expect the outreach to be particularly impactful in under-represented institutions and regions, mostly Asia.

Impact of outreach and training of new MSK software users and creators. In the past 2 years, the ORMIR community has grown from 9 to 30 participants. We expect the community to at least double, and that at least 40 members will follow us on Twitter. We estimate 50 views

per month for the whole website and 30 for the book webpages. We plan for 26 participants at Workshop 2, but we will be able to scale up to 50 participants. For the satellite workshop at QMSKI 2024, we expect at least 100 participants. Finally, we expect 1 publication about the whole certification framework, and 1 publication for each certified software, for a total of 13 publications.

B. PROJECT PROPOSAL

Abstract

Computational workflows are the core of quantitative musculoskeletal (MSK) imaging research. Although they share a similar structure, workflows are highly fragmented as they consist of a combination of proprietary software and in-house algorithms written in various languages. This fragmentation causes practical limitations, including impossibility to modify proprietary software, difficulties at comparing algorithm outputs, and loss of efficiency due to reimplementations. The recently founded Open and Reproducible Musculoskeletal Imaging Research (ORMIR) Community aspires to reduce fragmentation with code standardization, educational material, and targeted training. The first aim of this project is to increase interoperability of MSK open source software by creating a certification system. Grant applicants will create certification guidelines and infrastructure to homogenize code style, structure, and documentation for existing and new MSK open source software. The second aim is to accelerate dissemination and adoption of certified software within the MSK imaging community. Applicants will recruit and engage MSK imaging scientists through social media, an improved website, and satellite events. In addition, they will create educational material and train MSK developers in in-person workshops. With this advancement, MSK imaging scientists will be able to focus their time and effort on conducting data-driven studies to answer biomedical questions, improving existing code, and adapting established workflows to new technologies. Ultimately, open, reproducible, and interoperable software will enable more collaborations, favor multi-center studies, and facilitate studies in underrepresented institutions at any geographical location, providing rapid, shared advancement of the understanding, diagnosis, treatment, and management of MSK disorders on a global scale.

Background

Computational workflows are the core of quantitative musculoskeletal (MSK) imaging research. In MSK imaging research, we aim to extract quantitative information from medical images of bones, joints, and muscles to investigate diseases such as osteoporosis, arthritis, and muscular dystrophies, which affect 1.71 billion people worldwide [1]. Our computational workflows have a common structure: 1) Acquisition of images of the MSK system using computed tomography (CT) or magnetic resonance (MR), at the organ or tissue level; 2) Segmentation of images to identify and label structures of interest, typically bones, cartilage, and muscles; and 3) Computation of metrics to quantify organ or tissue composition, morphology, and mechanical properties and behavior. Workflow implementations can vary based on different anatomies of interest, image acquisition protocols, and algorithm parameters or implementations [2, 3].

The MSK imaging ecosystem is highly fragmented. Although research interests and workflow structures are similar, we experience an extreme computational fragmentation at a community

level (Figure 1). Workflows often consist of a combination of proprietary software—mainly provided by scanner manufacturers—and in-house algorithms, written either in proprietary languages (e.g. Matlab) or open source languages (e.g. C++, Python). Code fragmentation causes practical limitations, including impossibility to modify proprietary software, difficulties at comparing algorithm outputs, and loss of efficiency due to reimplementations. This scenario eventually leads to challenges for cross-institutional collaborations and decelerates scientific discoveries [4, 5].

To collectively implement solutions, we founded the Open and Reproducible Musculoskeletal Imaging Research (ORMIR) Community. Since 2019, we have jointly begun investigating and implementing pragmatic solutions for sharing and homogenizing our software. Our community currently includes 30 MSK imaging scientists from academic institutions in North America, Europe, the Middle East, and Australia, as well as industry partners [6]. Eleven of the members are applicants in this grant. Our initiatives have included five workshops (Table 1), where we have: 1) Increased awareness for open and reproducible workflows with the broader MSK imaging community; 2) Identified the Scientific Python and the Jupyter ecosystems as the infrastructures to adopt; and 3) Started implementing open and reproducible workflows. A pivotal event was the Jupyter Community Workshop held in June 2022, where we held sessions to train-the-trainers, contributed to three Python packages during hackathons, and learned from experts in modern infrastructures for open science (Lorena Barba and Chris Holdgraf). Other achievements of our community include two successful grant applications (Table 2) and quarterly virtual meetings to share updates and define directions and solutions.

To reduce fragmentation, we need code standardization, educational material, and targeted training. We aspire to create a collection of open, reproducible, and interoperable Python packages that can be used by the larger MSK imaging community, following the example of established suites, such as Nipy [7], the Scientific Python ecosystem, and Tidyverse [8]. At an organizational level, we aim to follow the path of established software communities in medical imaging (e.g. Neuroconductor [9]), biomedical sciences (e.g. Bioconductor [10]), and other disciplines (e.g. Pangeo [11]). To reach our goals, we need to overcome MSK software fragmentation through the creation of a software certification system, create educational material targeted to MSK scientists who are new to open software, and train MSK imaging developers to create interoperable software.

Project Goals

In this project, we want to accomplish the following two aims, focused on *building capacity*, and *training and education*:

- **Aim 1: To increase interoperability of MSK open source software by creating a certification system.** We will create certification guidelines and infrastructure to homogenize code style, structure, and documentation for existing and new MSK open source software.
- **Aim 2: To accelerate dissemination and adoption of certified software within the MSK imaging community.** We will recruit and engage MSK imaging scientists through

social media, an improved website, and events. We will also create educational material and train MSK developers at in-person workshops.

Significance

Developing and accelerating MSK software interoperability and dissemination will benefit MSK imaging scientists in daily research activities. By using certified code, MSK imaging scientists will be able to focus their time and effort on conducting data-driven studies to answer biomedical questions; reproduce other laboratories' results for verification; and compare results from different studies or algorithms. In addition, MSK imaging software developers will be able to focus on improving existing code via bug finding, new workarounds, or efficiencies (instead of re-implementing algorithms); adapting existing workflows to new technologies (e.g. adapting the BoneErosion package to images acquired with the novel Photon Counting CT (PCCT; [12])); and creating new code based on certified code. On a global scale, open, reproducible, and interoperable MSK software will make collaborations more effective, encourage multi-center studies, and facilitate studies in underrepresented institutions at any geographical location. In the longer term, this will lead to global, shared, and accelerated advancement of the understanding, diagnosis, treatment, and management of MSK disorders, both common and rare.

Project Plan

Our project consists of two parallel work packages, each matching a project aim. The executors will be the PI with the ten Co-PIs, together with their local teams, some of whom are part of the Technical Advisory Board (TAB) and Community Advisory Board (CAB) of the ORMIR community (see Figure 2). To support our work, we will hire a Research Software Engineer (RSE) part-time and a scientific writer for occasional contributions.

Work package 1: Creating and validating a certification framework for open, reproducible, and interoperable MSK imaging research software. Strategy. To reduce fragmentation of our software ecosystem and increase code interoperability, we will create a certification framework for existing and new MSK imaging computational projects, developed by members of the ORMIR community and of the broader MSK imaging community (Figure 1). This work package is focused on **building capacity**, which we will achieve in four phases and whose timeline is indicated in Figure 2:

- **Phase 1: Creating certification guidelines.** The RSE and the TAB will create guidelines that will require MSK computational projects to have a standard layout comprising: 1) A Python package or interface; 2) Jupyter Notebooks as use cases for tutorials (similar to R vignettes [13]); 3) A GitHub repository; and 4) Online documentation for developers and users. To facilitate guideline adoption, the RSE and TAB will create templates of Jupyter Notebooks, GitHub readme files, etc. to be adapted to the specific needs of each computational project. Details of the certification guidelines will be inspired by existing

renowned platforms and publication systems, such as Bioconductor [14], Pangeo [15], Neuroconductor [16], and JOSS [17].

- **Phase 2: Developing a certification framework.** The RSE will develop a certification framework matching the guidelines created during Phase 1. The core of the framework will be a static analyzer for code parsing implemented in Python, which will be hosted on GitHub and will expose a GitHub action for the projects' use. In addition, the RSE will create tests for Application Programming Interface (API) compatibility among projects to homogenize inputs and outputs. The certification framework will be automatic (as much as possible) for robustness, scalability, and easy future maintenance.
- **Phase 3: Validating the certification framework with six existing MSK computational projects.** RSE, TAB, and the contributors to six existing MSK computational projects will jointly work to test and validate the certification framework. Agile practices will be used to clarify certification guidelines, debug and streamline the certification framework, and ultimately converge to robustness and ease of use. The six projects, specified in Table 3, are representative of the variety of workflows in MSK imaging research, as they include various anatomies (knee, hand, femur, etc.), imaging modalities (CT, high-resolution CT, and MR), and quantitative outputs (morphology, tissue composition, and mechanical response).
- **Phase 4: Certifying new MSK computational projects.** We will open our certification system to the extended MSK imaging community. We will start certifying new software during one of our workshops and we will promote the certification framework in social media, conferences, and publications (see Work Package 2).

Outcomes and deliverables. On the [ORMIR community website](#), we will create one page for certification guidelines (Phase 1), and one page listing the certified projects (Phases 3 and 4). The final interface will have a simple but complete structure, similar to the Tutorial page on the Neuroconductor website [18]. The certification framework (Phase 2) will be hosted on GitHub. In general, we will concentrate effort in creating easy-to-read and precise interfaces and documentation, which will be streamlined by a subcontracted scientific writer.

Work Package 2: Accelerating adoption and creation of certified MSK imaging software by recruiting and engaging MSK imaging scientists, creating educational material, and providing in-person training and mentoring. To accelerate spread and development of open, reproducible, and interoperable software within the ORMIR and the larger MSK imaging community, we will focus on a combination of **building capacity** and **training and education**.

Strategy. We will complete the following three tasks, whose timeline is indicated in Figure 2:

- **Task 1: Recruiting and engaging MSK imaging scientists through social media, events at conferences, an improved website, and scientific publications.** The CAB will open and maintain a Twitter account to share activities of the ORMIR community (achievements, workshops, etc.) and communicate certification of new software. In addition, the CAB will redesign the [ORMIR community website](#), focusing on (1) improving clarity of narrative of existing sections (e.g. aims, about, how to navigate the website); (2) integrating meeting agenda and notes for open participation during community meetings; and (3) streamlining information about existing packages for software users and certification guidelines for software contributors. To receive

feedback from MSK software users and developers and increase new members enrolment, we will organize satellite events at conferences (e.g. a night workshop during QMSKI 2024). Finally, we will write scientific publications on the software certification framework and the certified packages.

- **Task 2: Creating an entry point for MSK imaging scientists who are new to open and reproducible software.** The CAB will design a specific webpage on the ORMIR community website containing streamlined information about activities and events, links to tutorials of certified packages (e.g. Jupyter Notebooks as vignettes—see Work Package 1, Phase 1), and to the electronic book developed during Workshop 1.

Workshop 1: Creating a Jupyter book on open and reproducible software in MSK imaging (Book sprint). During this three-day workshop, we will select, collect, and homogenize guidelines and tutorials from scientific journals, blogs, and videos, using reliable resources such as The Carpentries [19], the Ten Simple Rules collection [20], and NASA's Transform to Open Science [21]. We will combine the material in a Jupyter book specifically targeted to MSK imaging scientists (especially early career) who want to become familiar with open and reproducible software. Topics will include: 1) coding (e.g. Python syntax, Scientific Python, Python medical image analysis packages, and Jupyter ecosystem); 2) software engineering (e.g. version control and continuous integration using GitHub, code packaging, and testing), and 3) best practices (e.g. for software licensing, code citation, and reproducible workflows). Our book sprint will follow the path of previous successful experiences in the open science community [22,23,24,25]. Participants will include PI and Co-PIs, the RSE, and an additional 12 participants recruited among members of the ORMIR and extended QMSKI communities. The workshop will be organized by Fulvia Taddei (Co-PI in this proposal) and her group in October 2023 in Bologna (Italy). After the workshop, the book will be edited by a subcontracted scientific writer to harmonize style.

- **Task 3: In-person training and mentoring of new MSK software contributors.** Beyond the activities described in Task 1, we will organize a workshop for MSK imaging scientists who want to certify their software according to the ORMIR standards. **Workshop 2: Making your MSK imaging software open, reproducible, and interoperable (Train-the-end-users event).** This three-day workshop will be in conjunction with QMSKI, our biennial conference of reference, whose 24th edition will be organized by Kathryn Stok and Andrew Burghardt (Co-PIs in this proposal). Participants will be supported in standardizing the code of their work presented at QMSKI according to the ORMIR guidelines. Sessions will include guidance on packaging, testing, standardization of Python code, and reproducibility of Jupyter Notebooks. The PI, Co-PIs, and the RSE will organize sessions and mentor the MSK software developers. The workshop will be open to all participants of QMSKI, and especially to MSK imaging scientists at an early career stage. In addition, to incentivize the development of open, reproducible, and interoperable MSK imaging software, we will give awards to the three most open, reproducible, and interoperable MSK software packages during QMSKI, using funding from this proposal. This second workshop will

be in Melbourne (Australia), in October 2024, jointly organized by Kathryn Stok and Serena Bonaretti (PI of this proposal) with their teams.

Outcomes and deliverables. We will create an improved version of the [ORMIR community website](#), with pages specifically dedicated to new members. The website will include references to the CC-BY licensed Jupyter Book created during the book sprint in Workshop 1, and the new MSK projects certified during Workshop 2.

Project Metrics

To evaluate the success of MSK software certification and dissemination, we will evaluate (1) Number of certified software packages; (2) Number of shared software packages within the ORMIR community, and (3) Number of software downloads in the extended MSK imaging community. To assess the success of outreach and training of new MSK software users and creators, we will consider: (1) Number of new ORMIR community members and Twitter followers; (2) Traffic on ORMIR website as a whole, and specifically on book webpages; (3) Number of participants at Workshop 2 and other satellite events; and (4) Number of scientific publications.

Figures and Tables

Table 1: Events for Open and Reproducible MSK Research we have organized since 2019

Date	Title	Organizers	Associated event	Links	Outcomes
26 Feb 2019	Working group on standardization of quantitative metrics for 3D imaging	Andrew Burghardt et al.	QMSKI 2019	/	Raised awareness of need of shared code and data in the MSK imaging community
25 Feb 2019	Hands-on transparent QMSKI research: Open data, reproducible workflows	Serena Bonaretti	QMSKI 2019	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2577617	Identification of tools for shared code (e.g., Python and the Jupyter ecosystem) and data (e.g. Zenodo, Figshare)
9-11 June 2022	Building the Jupyter Community in MSK Imaging Research	Serena Bonaretti	/	https://github.com/JCMSK/2022_JCW/blob/main/README.md	Development of three Python packages (BoneErosion, Ciclope, Muscle-BIDS); Training of new members; Creation of Technical and Community Advisory Boards
13 June 2022	Introducing the Open and Reproducible Musculoskeletal Imaging Research (ORMIR) Community	Serena Bonaretti, Enrico Schileo (senior scientist with Fulvia Taddei), Sarah Manske	QMSKI 2022	/	Formally introduced the ORMIR community to the extended MSK imaging community; Recruited new members
13 June 2022	Are open and reproducible workflows necessary for CT in clinical trials and research?	Sarah Manske, Kathryn Stok, Andrew Burghardt, Andy Kin On Wong, et al.	QMSKI 2022	/	Increased awareness of need of shared code and data within the extended MSK imaging community by debating pros and cons

Notes:

- QMSKI (Quantitative Musculoskeletal Imaging) is our conference of reference (<https://qmski.org/>). It is usually held biannually, but the 2021 edition was postponed to 2022 because of the COVID pandemic. The workshop 2 we propose in this application will be held in conjunction with QMSKI 2024, which will be organized by Kathryn Stok and Andrew Burghardt.
- The workshop "Building the Jupyter Community in MSK Imaging Research" was held after a 2 year delay because of the COVID pandemic.

Table 2. Successful funding applications we have written since 2020

Acceptance date	Title	Applicants	Funding Agency	Status
January 2020	Building the Jupyter Community in MSK Imaging Research	Serena Bonaretti, Andrew Burghardt, Fulvia Taddei, Sarah Manske, Kathryn Stok, et al.	Bloomberg and Amazon Web Services via NumFocus	Completed
June 2022	Development of an open-source reference data set, image repository and interactive training tool for bone damage assessment in inflammatory arthritis	Sarah Manske, Kathryn Stok, Andrew Burghardt, Serena Bonaretti, et al.	Canadian Institute of Health Research	In progress

Figure 1. Software ecosystem in MSK imaging research. (Top) Currently, after acquisition and export, images are processed with a plurality of proprietary and in-house software collected in fragmented workflows, slowing the pace of scientific discoveries. (Bottom) Thanks to this project, images will be processed with open, reproducible, and interoperable software in homogenized workflows, potentially accelerating scientific discoveries.

	Year:	1 (2023 - 2024)				2 (2024 - 2025)			
		Quarter:		3rd 4th		5th 6th		7th 8th	
		Months:	03-05	06-08	09-11	12-02	03-05	06-08	09-11
WP 1: Creating and validating a certification framework for MSK software	1: Creating certification guidelines (RSE + TAB) 2: Developing certification framework (RSE + TAB) 3: Validating the framework (RSE+TAB+CPC) 4: Certifying new MSK projects (RSE + TAB)	[Gantt chart showing activity from 03-05 to 12-02]				[Gantt chart showing activity from 03-05 to 12-02]			
WP 2: Accelerating adoption and creation of certified MSK software	1: Recruiting and engaging MSK scientists (CAB) 2: Creating online educational material (PI + Co-PIs) 3: In-person training and mentoring (PI + Co-PIs)	WS 1				WS 2			

Acronyms: WP: Work Package; RSE: Research Software Engineer (Pablo Hernandez-Cerdan); TAB: Technical Advisory Board (Donnie Cameron, Gianluca Iori, Serena Bonaretti, and Michelle Alejandra Espinoza Hernandez, a PhD student co-supervised by Andy Kin On Wong and Kathryn Stok); CAB: Community Advisory Board (Francesco Santini, Martino Pani, Kathryn Stok, and Serena Bonaretti); CPC: Computational Project Contributors (PI and all 10 Co-PIs); WS: Workshop

Figure 2. Timeline of our project

Table 3. Details of the six computational projects we will certify during Phase 3 of Work Package 1

Project name	GitHub repository / Documentation	Description	Contributors	Publications	Funding resources
BoneErosion	https://github.com/SpectraCollab/ORMIR_2022	Processing of High Resolution CT images to quantify bone damage in rheumatoid arthritis	Sarah Manske, Andrew Burghardt, Kathryn Stok, Andy Wong, and 5 early career contributors	[26], JOSS (in preparation)	CIHR Planning and Dissemination Grant "Development of an open-source reference data set, image repository and interactive training tool for bone damage assessment in inflammatory arthritis" and NumFOCUS (during the Jupyter Community Workshop)
Ciclope	https://github.com/gianthk/ciclope https://ciclope.readthedocs.io/en/latest/	Processing of micro Computed Tomography (microCT) 3D images to generate Finite Element (FE) models	Gianluca Iori, Martino Pani, Fulvia Taddei, and 3 more contributors (1 early career)	JOSS (in preparation), JMBBM (in preparation)	Volunteering contributions and NumFOCUS (during the Jupyter Community Workshop)
Muscle BIDS	https://github.com/muscle-bids/muscle-bids	Conversion and I/O support tool and library for multi vendor Muscle MRI data in standardized format	Francesco Santini, Donnie Cameron, and 9 more contributors (2 early career)	ISMRM 2023 (in preparation), MRI Together 2023 (in preparation)	Volunteering contributions and NumFOCUS (during the Jupyter Community Workshop)
ALBA	https://github.com/IOR-BIC/ALBA	Framework for the rapid development of imaging-based musculoskeletal applications.	Fulvia Taddei, and 3 more contributors (1 early career)	SoftwareX (in preparation)	Partially supported during development (2017 - on going) by two grants from the Italian Ministry of Health (RF-2018-12368274 and RF-2016-02364359).
pyKNEEr	https://github.com/sbonaretti/pyKNEEr https://sbonaretti.github.io/pyKNEEr/	Workflow to segment and quantify morphometry and relaxometry of femoral knee cartilage from MR images	Serena Bonaretti	[27,28]	Currently, volunteering contributions. During development (2016-2018), first and last authors by Merit Review award I01 RX001811 from the United States Department of Veterans Affairs; second author by NIH R01 EB002524 and K24
OAI analysis	https://github.com/uncbiag/OAI_analysis_2	Deep-learning based segmentation, registration, and atlas-based analysis of knee cartilage thickness	Marc Niethammer, and 3 more contributors (1 early career)	[29]	The project is currently supported by an NIH grant which will provide support until mid 2023: R01 AR072013 and R44 AR074375.

Note: PI / Co-PI refers to this grant, not to the computational project

Acronyms: JOSS: Journal of Open Source Software; JMBBM: Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Biomedical Materials; ISMRM: International Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine (Conference); QMSKI: Quantitative Musculoskeletal Imaging (Conference)

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